

SOCIO-ECONOMIC STATUS AS A CORRELATE OF ADVERSITY QUOTIENT OF HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS

Dr. Neeru Rathee* & Sushila Sharma**

* Assistant Professor, Department of Education, M.D University,
Rohtak, Haryana

** Senior Research Fellow, Department of Education, M.D University,
Rohtak, Haryana

Cite This Article: Dr. Neeru Rathee & Sushila Sharma, "Socio-Economic Status as a Correlate of Adversity Quotient of High School Students", International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Modern Education, Volume 4, Issue 1, Page Number 117-124, 2018.

Copy Right: © IJMRME, R&D Modern Research Publication, 2018 (All Rights Reserved). This is an Open Access Article distributed under the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium provided the original work is properly cited.

Abstract:

The present study examines the socio-economic status as a correlate of Adversity Quotient among high school students. A representative sample of 400 (200 male and 200 female) high school students from urban and rural background was selected by employing multistage random sampling technique choosing one district each from North, East, West, South and Central Zones of Haryana state. Adversity Quotient Assessment Scale (self developed) by Rathee and Sharma (2015) and Socio Economic Status Scale by Kalia and Sahu (2014) were used to assess Adversity Quotient and Socio-economic Status of high school students. The study revealed a significant difference between high Socio Economic Status and Low Socio Economic Status high school students on Adversity Quotient. But gender and locality does not mark any difference between High Socio Economic Status and Low Socio Economic Status high school students. Pearson's product moment correlation was used to study relationship between Adversity Quotient and Socio-Economic Status among high school students. The study revealed that there exist significant positive correlation between Adversity Quotient and Socio Economic Status

Key Words: Adversity Quotient & Socio-Economic Status

Introduction:

Everybody has to face difficult and challenging situations in their lives. Some bravely stands against them, some fight with the adversities with some half hearted courage while some easily loose themselves in the waves of sufferings. The ability of an individual to fight against adversities and bouncing potential is known as resilience. Dr. Stolz in 1997 popularizes the concept by giving it new term with wider essence as 'Adversity Quotient' in his famous book "*Turning obstacles into opportunities*" and explained it '*as science of resilience*'. He described resilience in a more scientific way by combing and refining several psychological constructs and theoretical frameworks. He developed a scientific measurement for determining resilience worldwide which achieved a great success in the form of Adversity Quotient Profile (ARP®). Stolz's adversity quotient was based on four dimensions

- ✓ Control: means ability to have a perceived control over adversities.
- ✓ Origin and Ownership: it reflects the accountability and responsibility and bringing improvement against the adversities one met.
- ✓ Reach: denotes one's ability to resist or getting sensitive against the adversities that whether they affect ones' other aspects of life or not.
- ✓ Endurance: exhibiting one's potential that how long one can affect from adversity.

Adversity Quotient is gaining a momentum since its discovery. Why resilience as Adversity Quotient? The probable answer for this question is that if I.Q stands for one's intellectuality and E.Q measures one's emotional aspect and even a new Quotient i.e S.Q means Spiritual Quotient measuring one's moral intelligence then it is quite rationale to give a new scientific quotient to resilience as 'Adversity Quotient' which contain several aspects of resilience which might earlier lagged to absorb within it. There arise several questions against the supremacy of intelligent quotient and other quotients (E.Q, and S.Q Etc.). History is full of examples where highly intelligent people and emotionally more stable persons loose themselves in the face of adversities they met in their life. Therefore in this paper adversity quotient is taken as one the variable for investigation for the present study. Another correlate taken for the research in association with adversity quotient is socio-economic status. As social stratification has been remained a pervasive phenomenon throughout the human history but its roots are more prevalent in India. No area and field has remained untouched where socio-economic status of a person does not affect his/her life. SES means the level in which a family lives according to their income, occupation and level of education. Socio-economic status is one of the important factor that affects not only adult's life but also influence a lot the student's life since from pre-schooling to their life time. Socio-economic status help in developing proper cognitive ability and performance and persist throughout the stages of development, (Gottfried, Bathurst, Guerin & Parramore, 2003). It is a general fact that high Socio-Economic

standard of a family may be able to fully fill all basic needs of an adolescent and directly or indirectly influence all aspects of his/her life. Students come from various socio-economic classes, values, intelligence, capacity, ideas; ambitions of the students vary according to their socio-economic status. Matenet al. (2006) examined that disadvantaged children, with low SES and less positive family qualities were generally less competent and more likely to be disruptive at high stress levels (Finkelstein, Kubzansky, Capitman and Goodman, 2007) which in turn may affect their performance and at times retention in schools, a negative impact has been found on physical, psychological well-being, emotional and cognitive functioning areas that affect brain development, academic success and social competence. Students subjected to such stress may lack crucial coping skills and experience significant behavioural and academic problems in schools. A child who comes from a stressful home environment tends to channel that stress into disruptive behaviour at school and be less able to develop a healthy social and academic life (Bradley & Corwyn, 2002). Behaviour research shows that children from impoverished homes develop psychiatric disturbances and maladaptive social functioning at a greater rate than their affluent counterparts do (McCoy, Firck, Loney & Ellia, 1999). Students from poor socio-economic status are more susceptible to hopelessness, despair and fatalism (Bradley and Corwyn 2002). Once students are in school, the dual factors of socialization and social status contribute significantly to behaviour. The school socialization process typically pressures students to be like their peer or risk social rejection. Literature surveyed on socio-economic status revealed that socio-economic background of the parent's influences academic performance of their children to a great extent (Panday and Maikhuri, 2003). Children belonging to high socio-economic status have access to more educational facilities/material than others which leads to good academic performance. SES is a marker for home life conditions.

Related Literature:

Socio-economic status is strongly associated with a number of indices of children's cognitive ability, including IQ, achievement tests, grade retention rates and literacy (Smith, Brooks-Gunn & Klebanov, 1997). The poorer the family, the less likely the child is ready in terms of schooling-related enablers: habits, vocabulary, thinking, and experience. Poorer children have access to inferior schools compared to children of the more wealthy Corollary (Grant Wiggin, 2012).

Many low socio-economic students are found to be suffering with emotional trauma and social instability. The lack of emotional nurturing can lead to feelings of alienation, inadequacy, depression and anxiety and social instability leading to insecurity during the early childhood years (Van et.al, 2004). Unfortunately, children who don't know how to develop proper emotions or appropriately respond to others the failure arises as to form positive relationships with peers and develop a long-term socio-emotional consequences (Szewcyk Sokolowski, Bost & Wain-Wright, 2005). Children require healthy learning and exploration for optimal brain development. Unfortunately, impoverished families tend to be a higher prevalence of adverse factors like teen motherhood, depression and inadequate health care (Van et.al, 2004). Therefore, SES poses several types of adversities on school-going students (Brettd, 2011). Devkumar (as cited by Villaver, in 2005). Fergusson (2003) cited in his work "Resilience of Childhood Adversity", found that measures of adversity are classified into four groups of related measures: i) measures of socio-economic adversity; ii) measures of parental change and conflict; iii) measures of child abuse; and iv) measures of parental adjustment problems. It has been reported in the region of one child in four from a family of low socio-economic status, and in one third of families both parents lacked formal educational qualifications. Socioeconomic adversity, involves those living in the lower level of socioeconomic status who typically fall below the poverty level of income, have a high school education or less, and work low-paying, often minimum wage jobs. Students from low socio-economic status or from disadvantaged groups score low on adversity quotient and sometimes have been found committing juvenile crimes and child abuse (Fergusson (2003)). It has been found that low family background is significantly correlated with delinquent behavior of students (Jalaja (1999)). It has been found out that success in schools for the students may be determined by their HSES. As childhood adversity significantly increases the risk of depression. Review of related literature carried out in the field of Adversity Quotient reflects that very few systematic attempts have been made to assess Adversity Quotient of high school students in Indian conditions. As there is a scarcity in research work done in the field of Adversity Quotient Therefore it is essential to carry out some empirical research that whether socio-economic status act as a correlate of Adversity Quotient of high school students or not.

Objectives:

- ✓ O₁. To compare and determine the difference between high socio-economic status and low socio-economic status of high school students on Adversity Quotient
- ✓ O₂. To compare and determine the difference between high socio-economic status male and high socio-economic status female high school student on Adversity Quotient
- ✓ O₃. To compare and determine the difference between low socio-economic status male and low socio-economic status female high school students on Adversity Quotient
- ✓ O₄. To compare and determine the difference between high socio-economic status urban and high socio-economic status rural high school students on Adversity Quotient

- ✓ O₅. To compare and determine the difference between low socio-economic status urban and low socio-economic status rural high school students on Adversity Quotient
- ✓ O₆. To study the relationship between Adversity Quotient and socio-economic status of high school students

Hypotheses:

- ✓ H₁. There exists no significant difference between high socio-economic status and low socio-economic status of high school students on Adversity Quotient
- ✓ H₂. There exists no significant difference between high socio-economic status male and high socio-economic status female high school students on Adversity Quotient
- ✓ H₃. There exists no significant difference between low socio-economic status male and low socio-economic status female high school students on Adversity Quotient
- ✓ H₄. There exists no significant difference between high socio-economic status urban and high socio-economic status rural high school students on Adversity Quotient
- ✓ H₅. There exists no significant difference between low socio-economic status urban and low socio-economic status rural high school students on Adversity Quotient
- ✓ H₆. There exists no significant relationship between Adversity Quotient and socio-economic status of high school students

Method and Procedure:

The study undertaken to determine the Socio-Economic Status as co-relates of Adversity Quotient among high school students of 9th class belonging to rural and urban areas. The investigator had employed descriptive survey method for the present study. In order to collect the data, Adversity Quotient Assessment and Socio-Economic Status scale were administered on male and female high school students. The scores of high school students in these scales were tabulated and analyzed by using appropriate statistical techniques.

Sample:

A sample of 400 High school students (200 Male and 200 Female) of 9th class was selected from one district each from five zones of Haryana state (north, east, west, south and central) by employing multistage random sampling technique from 25 secondary schools located in urban and rural areas.

Measures Used:

- ✓ Adversity Quotient Assessment Scale: Tool is constructed and standardized by Rathee and Sharma (2015, unpublished)
- ✓ Socio-economic Status Scale (SESS) developed by Kalia and Sahu (2014)

Statistical Techniques Employed:

Mean and S.Ds, t-test and Correlation were used for Analysis of the data.

Analysis and Interpretations:

The collected data were classified, tabulated and subjected to statistical analysis using Mean, S.Ds and correlation. The interpretation of the collected data is as follows:

Table 1: Mean, SD's, SEMs & 't' Ratios of High Socio-Economic Status High School Students and Low Socio-Economic Status High School Students on Adversity Quotient

S.No	Dimensions of Adversity Quotient	High Socio-Economic Status (N=197)			Low Socio-Economic Status (N=203)			't' -Value
		Mean	S.D	SEM	Mean	S.D	SEM	
1	Control	45.32	6.88	0.490	43.69	6.41	0.449	2.450*
2	Origin	54.54	7.94	0.565	52.46	9.00	0.631	2.448*
3	Reach	44.29	7.51	0.535	42.49	6.73	0.472	2.521*
4	Endurance	44.02	9.32	0.664	44.13	9.56	0.671	0.116
5	Global Adversity Quotient	188.18	19.904	1.418	182.78	20.007	1.404	2.705**

** $P \leq 0.01 = 2.59$, * $P \leq 0.05 = 1.97$, $Df = 398$

It is clear from the table 1 that on the mean score of High Socio-Economic Status students (188.18) is higher than the mean score of Low Socio-Economic Status students (182.78) on global adversity Quotient, 't' ratio is 2.705. Which is significant at 0.01 level. The higher mean score of High Socio-Economic Status indicates that they are less sensitive to high adversities and are more positively responding to adverse conditions in comparison to Low Socio-Economic Status High school students. The results also indicates that High Socio-Economic Status high school students are significantly higher on all the dimensions of Adversity Quotient in comparison to low Socio-Economic Status high school students i.e control, Origin & Ownership and reach dimension of Adversity Quotient except Endurance. But both the groups are similar on Endurance dimension of Adversity Quotient. Therefore, the proposed hypothesis 'H₁' has been rejected (as shown in Figure 1)

Table 2: Mean, SD's, SEM's, & 't' Ratio of High Socio-Economic Status Male and High Socio-Economic Status Female High School Students on Adversity Quotient

S.No	Dimensions of Adversity Quotient	High Socio-Economic Status Male (N=112)			High Socio-Economic Status Female (N=85)			't' - Value
		Mean	S.D.	SEM	Mean	S.D.	SEM	
1.	Control	43.25	6.78	0.640	45.74	6.67	0.723	2.570*
2.	Origin	53.65	8.38	0.791	55.71	7.19	0.779	1.815
3.	Reach	44.0	8.16	0.771	44.64	6.60	0.715	0.591
4.	Endurance	45.60	9.32	0.880	44.24	9.31	1.009	1.014
5.	Global Adversity Quotient	186.54	20.445	1.932	190.35	19.070	2.068	1.336

* $P \leq 0.05 = 1.97$, $DF = 195$

Table 2 illustrate that High Socio-Economic Status Female High school students do not differ with High Socio-Economic Status Male students on Global Adversity Quotient. It is inferred from the results that both the groups are similar on Adversity Quotient. But can be depicts that High Socio-Economic Status Female students are significantly higher on Control dimension of Adversity Quotient while on rest of all the dimensions of adversity quotient i.e Origin and ownership, reach, endurance they exhibit similar Adversity Quotient. Therefore, the proposed hypothesis "H₂" has been retained. (as shown in fig.2)

Table 3: Mean, SD's, SEM's, & 't' Ratio of Low Socio-Economic Status Male and Low Socio-Economic Status Female High School Students on Adversity Quotient

S.No	Dimensions of Adversity Quotient	Low Socio-Economic Status Male (N=88)			Low Socio-Economic Status Female (N=115)			't' - Value
		Mean	S.D	SEM	Mean	S.D	SEM	
1.	Control	44.47	6.76	0.720	43.09	6.10	0.568	1.520
2.	Origin	52.61	8.98	0.957	52.34	9.06	0.844	0.211
3.	Reach	42.12	6.64	0.707	42.77	6.82	0.636	0.680
4.	Endurance	45.27	10.25	1.092	43.26	8.94	0.833	1.489
5.	Global Adversity Quotient	184.49	19.734	2.104	181.48	20.20	1.884	1.063

Not significant at any level, DF=201

It can be inferred from table 3 that the High Socio-Economic Status Male High school students and Low Socio-Economic Status Female High school students are on all the dimensions of Adversity Quotient at any level. It indicates that they have equal Adversity Quotient on all the dimensions of adversity quotient i.e Control, Origin and Ownership, Reach and Endurance. Therefore, the proposed hypothesis-3 has been retained in the present study (as shown in figure 3).

Table 4: Mean, SD's, SEM's, & 't' Ratio of High Socio-Economic Status Urban and High Socio-Economic Status Rural High School Students on Adversity Quotient

S.No	Dimensions of Adversity Quotient	High Socio-Economic Status Urban (N=93)			High Socio-Economic Status Rural (N=88)			't' - Value
		Mean	S.D	SEM	Mean	S.D	SEM	
1.	Control	44.64	6.81	0.706	43.70	6.89	0.734	0.922
2.	Origin	52.87	7.91	0.820	56.36	8.00	0.852	2.950*
3.	Reach	44.46	7.09	0.735	43.98	8.26	0.880	0.420
4.	Endurance	45.71	9.19	0.953	44.34	9.48	1.010	0.987
5.	Global Adversity Quotient	187.70	19.939	1.910	188.78	19.958	2.128	0.38

*P≤0.05=1.97, Df=179

Table 4.shows the means scores of High Socio-Economic Status urban ((M=187.70±19.939) and high Socio-Economic Status Rural High school students (M=188.78±19.958) which indicates that no significant different is exist on global Adversity Quotient at any level. Also No significant difference was found on rest of other dimensions of Adversity Quotient also i.e control, Reach and endurance, It means that both the groups are similar on control, reach, and endurance except origin and ownership on Adversity Quotient. Therefore, the stated hypothesis-4 has been retained.

Table 5: Mean, SD's, SEM's, & 't' Ratio of Low Socio-Economic Status Urban and Low Socio-Economic Status Rural High School Students on Adversity Quotient

S.No	Dimensions of Adversity Quotient	Low Socio-Economic Status Urban (N=107)			Low Socio-Economic Status Rural (N=112)			't' - Value
		Mean	S.D	SEM	Mean	S.D	SEM	
1.	Control	43.68	6.67	0.644	43.89	6.26	0.591	0.240
2.	Origin	52.50	7.37	0.712	52.41	10.01	0.945	0.075
3.	Reach	43.38	5.99	0.579	41.71	6.96	0.657	1.899
4.	Endurance	45.53	7.30	0.705	42.76	11.01	1.040	2.183*
5.	Global Adversity Quotient	185.11	14.722	1.543	180.61	23.452	2.236	1.590

* $P \leq 0.01 = 1.97$, $DF = 199$

It is clear from the table 5 that low Socio-Economic Status urban and low Socio-Economic Status Rural High school students are equal on global Adversity Quotient. On rest of the dimensions of Adversity Quotient i.e Control, Origin and Ownership and Reach, both the groups have similar Adversity Quotient on Control, Origin and ownership and Reach. Therefore, the above stated hypothesis-5 that, has been retained (Fig.5)

Table 6: Relationship Between Adversity Quotient and Socio-Economic Status Of High School Students

Groups	N	r-value	Level of significance
Academic Stress	400	0.116*	0.05 level
Socio-Economic Status	400		

Table 6 shows that the obtained 'r' value between Socio-Economic Status and Adversity Quotient of High School Students is a significantly positive at 0.05 level of significance. This indicates that higher the Socio-Economic Status higher will be the Adversity Quotient of high school students. Therefore, the proposed hypothesis-6 that, has been rejected. (Fig.6)

Conclusions:

- ✓ High socio-economic statuses significantly differ from low socio-economic status of high school students on Global Adversity Quotient and on all the dimensions i.e Control, Origin and Ownership and Reach of Adversity Quotient except Endurance.
- ✓ No significant difference was found between high socio-economic status of male and female high school students on Global Adversity Quotient and on all the dimensions i.e Origin and Ownership, Reach and Endurance of Adversity Quotient except Control.
- ✓ Both low socio-economic status male and low socio-economic status female high school students have similar on Global Adversity Quotient and all the dimensions of Adversity Quotient.
- ✓ High socio-economic status urban did not differ from high socio-economic status rural high school students on Adversity Quotient and on all the dimensions of Adversity Quotient i.e Control, Reach and Endurance except on Origin and Ownership.
- ✓ No significant difference was found between low socio-economic status urban and low socio-economic status rural high school students on Global Adversity Quotient i.e Control, Origin and Ownership, Reach and except on Endurance.
- ✓ A significant positive relationship was found between Adversity Quotient and Socio-Economic Status of high school students.

References:

1. Bradley, R. H. & Corwyn, R. F. (2002). Socioeconomic status and child development. Annual Review of Psychology, 53, 371-399.
2. Brett, D., Nelson Izadnegahdar R, Hall L, Lee PT (2011). Global health fellowship training: a national, cross-disciplinary survey [abstract] Paper presented at: 139th American Public Health Association Annual Meeting; October 29–November 2,; Washington, DC
3. Devakumar, M. (2012). A Study of Adversity Quotient of Secondary School Students in Relation to their Academic Self Concept and Achievement Motivation, Retrieved from http://www.peaklearning.com/documents/PEAK_GRI_devakumar2.pdf
4. Finkelstein DM, Kubzansky LD, Capitman J, Goodman E.(2008) Socioeconomic differences in adolescent stress: the role of psychological resources. J Adolesc Health. 2007 Feb; 40(2):127-34.
5. Fergusson DM, Horwood LJ. (2003). Reliance in Childhood Adversity: Results of a 21 Year Study. Published by Cambridge University Press
6. Gottfried, A. W., Gottfried, A. E., Bathurst, K., Guerin, D. W. & Parramore, M. M. (2003). Socioeconomic status in children's development and family environment, Infancy through adolescence. In M.H. Bornstein & R.H. Bradley (Eds), Socio economic status, parenting and child development. Mahwah, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.
7. Grant Wiggan, (2012). 10 Theories On The Relationship Between Socioeconomic Status & Academic Achievement, <http://www.teachthought.com/uncategorized/10-theories-on-the-relationship-between-socioeconomic-status-and-academic-achievement/>)

8. Greg J. Duncan and Jeanne Brooks-Gunn (1997). *Consequences of Growing Up Poor* Published by: Russell Sage Foundation. Pages: 672. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/10.7758/9781610448260>
9. Jalaja (1999). *A Study of Certain Factors Leads to Juvenile Delinquency*. M.Ed. thesis, Regional Institute of Education, Mysore.
10. Kalia, A.K & Sahu (2014). *Manual of Socio Economic Status Scale*, Agra. National Psychological Corporation.
11. McCoy M B, Firck P J, Loney B R, Ellis M L (1999). The potential mediating role of parenting practices in the development of conduct problems in a clinic-referred sample. *Journal of Child and Family Studies*; 8:477-94.
12. Pandey, S. K. and Maikhuri, R. (2003). "Socio-Economic Status and Academic Achievement", *Journal in Psycho Lingua*, 33 (1), 60-64.
13. Stoltz, P. (1997). *Adversity quotient: Turning obstacles into opportunities*. New York, Wiley, ISBN 978-0471344131
14. Stephens, J. M. and Nicholson, H. (2008). Cases of incongruity: exploring the divide between adolescents' beliefs and behavior related to academic dishonesty. *Educational Studies*. 34(4), 361–376
15. Szewczyk-Sokolowski, M., Bost, K. K. & Wainwright, A. B. (2005). Attachment, temperament and preschool children's peer acceptance. *Social Development*, 14, 379- 397.
16. Rathee, N., Sharma, S (2015). *Adversity Quotient Assessment Scale*. (Unpublished)
17. Van Ijzendoorn, M. H., Vereijken, C. M. J. L., Bakermans-Kranenburg, M. J. & Riken- Walraven, M. J. (2004). Assessing attachment security with the attachment of sort Meta-analytic evidence for the validity of the observe AQS. *Child Development*, 75(4), 1188-1213.
18. Villaver, E. L. (2005). *Adversity Quotient levels of Female Grade School Teachers of a Public and a Private School in Rizal Province*. St. Joseph's College, Quezon City.